

RM ROADMAP

D4.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan

The RM-ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) Plan is a live document, developed with the RM-ROADMAP consortium and structured to act as a practical working reference for all consortium team members when performing their own tasks.

The DCE Plan defines targets, protocols, and projected schedules for DCE activities.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

**“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to
Strengthen the European Research Area”**

**Project acronym
RM Roadmap**

**Grant Agreement no.
101058475**

D4.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan

RM Roadmap_CHX_WP4_D4.1_Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan

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Project Overview

RM-ROADMAP aims to support and strengthen our research management (RM) capacity in Europe. Over 36 months, the project charts a course for the future of EU research management (RM) and creates an inclusive community to support its delivery.

The overarching goal of RM Roadmap is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

RM Roadmap will allow existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented consultation process for RM. This co-creation process will gather the existing communities and expand upon them to reach two main objectives:

- To create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap.
- To inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners are working together on this exciting project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

The success of this project depends on the involvement of the entire research management community. We encourage research support professionals of all levels to participate in RM-Roadmap. Join us, share your views and work with us to shape the future of the research management profession in Europe.

1. INTRODUCTION

The RM-ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) Plan is a live document, developed with the RM-ROADMAP consortium and structured to act as a practical working reference for all consortium team members when performing their own tasks. DCE is an integral part of our development processes, and while it is managed and administered from WP4 (Communication, Dissemination and Community Building) and WP6 (Sustainability and Exploitation), DCE activities may arise in all tasks across all WPs.

The DCE Plan defines targets, protocols, and projected schedules for DCE activities.

DCE implementation began formally at project kick-off, while planning and preparatory activities have taken place continuously from before the project term. This deliverable therefore represents the plan at M6, and a brief report on activities to date.

An updated report on DCE activities, including any changes and additions to the plan, will be delivered at M24 (D4.4), with a final report published at M34 (D4.6) close to the end of the project.

1.1. Purpose and Objectives of the Plan

The DCE Plan provides a framework for the project to engage with key stakeholders and audiences. It defines the tools and strategies the project will leverage to increase awareness, increase targeted availability of results and de-risk, and improve exploitation potential.

RM-ROADMAP's communications objectives

- Raise awareness of the project and its progress with key audiences
- Develop a project identity, website, and social media presence.
- Develop standard materials for the consortium partners to use in communications activities.
- Identify opportunities to multiply the effectiveness of communications, such as project clusters and networks.
- Analyse communications to identify stakeholder categories and groupings for targeted dissemination and exploitation.

RM-ROADMAP's dissemination objectives

- Disseminate results among the RM community to be used, adopted and/or implemented directly, and to initiate and facilitate further work.
- Disseminate results to relevant public agencies responsible for funding research, to support effective integration of future RM activities into research programmes.

RM-ROADMAP's exploitation objectives

- Identify and further define key exploitable results and map pathways to impact.
- Engage with key stakeholders on the impact pathway as early as possible.

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- Develop and implement sustainability measures to ensure long-term exploitation of the project outcomes.

1.2. Evolution of DC&E over the project term

Activity will develop throughout the project, and beyond, as shown in Figure 1. The initial phase focuses on raising awareness, initiating stakeholder mapping, and agreeing strategies. For the remainder of the project term, stakeholder analysis continues and produces an engagement strategy to be implemented such that communications, dissemination of results and stakeholder engagement work together to support the achievement of *PROJECT*'s impact goals. Later versions of this deliverable will further explore sustainability of our activities.

Figure 1: Evolution of DCE through the project

2. PROJECT AUDIENCES

Through proposal development and at the project kick-off, the consortium has identified categories of stakeholder that have an interest in or influence on RM-ROADMAP or are going to be affected in some way by our progress and expected results. These groups may be considered audiences for the purpose of communication and dissemination. Their relationship with respect to exploitation may be more complex and is explored in more detail in the later sections of this plan.

The RM-ROADMAP partners have initiated a process to develop a strategic approach to each category/audience, and to list key stakeholders within each category. Stakeholder mapping actions taking place in WP1 (Intelligence) and WP2 (Training and Development) is consolidated into a single dataset, managed by Crowdhelix under WP4.

This process will continue throughout the project, and categories may be further subdivided and refined, for example by geographical area of operation, or specific interest within the RM domain.

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Audience category	Description (with respect to RM-ROADMAP)	Specific objectives, messaging	Standard communication channels and content types
Academic RTOs - RM Professionals	Offices in research-led academic universities and institutes where research managers are employed	For RM to join the project's community building and engagement tasks, and to receive information on training and networking activities	Knowledge and Community Platform Project Website Social Media Newsletters Appearances at target events (Appendix B)
Academic RTOs - Academics	Research-led academic universities and institutes where research is being conducted, supported by RMs and potentially on RM as a scientific domain	To clarify the role and potential for RM to support academic activities. To engage with active research groups on RM topics to further the knowledge domain.	Knowledge and Community Platform (<i>specifically the RM Helix</i>) Project Website Social Media Newsletters Appearances at target events (Appendix B)
Public agencies	Funding agencies for national and international research and innovation programmes, and their governing directorates	To clarify the role and potential for RM to support the ERA and overall R&I System	Public deliverables Policy briefs Newsletters Appearances at target events (Appendix B) Direct contact
NGOs and non-profits	Non-profit associations including national associations for professional staff in the domain of research management	Utilised to recruit ambassadors and spread information to academic RTOs	Newsletters Direct contact to initiate ambassador recruitment
Policy makers	Government agencies and their associated consultancies and think-tanks with an influence on or interest in European RM	To clarify the role and potential for RM to support the ERA and overall R&I System	Public deliverables Policy briefs Newsletters Appearances at target events (Appendix B) Direct contact
Commercial RTOs	Research-driven companies employing research managers and/or engaging with academic RTOs on collaborative projects	To clarify the role and potential for RM to support the ERA and overall R&I System	Project Website Social Media Newsletters Appearances at target events (Appendix B)
Commercial industry	Companies that may adopt the results of research and innovation in RTOs	To clarify the role and potential for RM to support the ERA and overall R&I System	Project Website Appearances at target events (Appendix B)
Civil society	General public with an interest in the conduct of research in RTOs, that may be engaging with research through citizen-science actions, or impacted by the results of research	To improve the understanding of the role of RM in supporting R&I	Press release / popularised article Project Website Social Media
Citizen	Organisations that represent	Utilised to spread information to	Press release / popularised article

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Audience category	Description (with respect to RM-ROADMAP)	Specific objectives, messaging	Standard communication channels and content types
Organisations	and/or advocate for civil society	civil society, and potentially to represent them in consultation tasks	Project Website Social Media Direct contact
Project or association	A research project, programme or association that may be conducted by a grouping of mixed audiences from the above categories	To multiply the above messages and to identify more organisations in the above audience categories	Newsletters Social Media Direct contact, private meetings
Exploitation partners	Organisations that may be able to utilise the results of the RM-ROADMAP project, for commercial, policy or further research. To be better defined in the execution of WP6.	To invite to engage with RM-ROADMAP to assist and validate planning exploitation and sustainability measures, and to prepare connections for implementing those measures.	To be defined

Table 1: RM-ROADMAP Audiences

3. OVERALL STRATEGY

To engage the above audiences, the project will leverage both traditional and digital marketing tools, project management and research methodologies and best practices.

As a project with co-creation at its heart, RM-ROADMAP's DCE plan is strategically aligned to the community building and maintaining tasks and objectives.

3.1. Clustering

Clusters, in the context of Horizon Europe, consist of related projects and initiatives with similar thematic focus and inter-dependent research activities that come together in common actions, events or meetings and share concepts, ideas and problems as well as communication and dissemination activities.

With respect to DCE, clustering objectives for RM-ROADMAP include:

- Amplify the reach of communication and dissemination activities
- Avoid duplication in efforts and confusion in messaging to the same audiences
- Share information that supports mutual success for projects in the cluster
- Ensure the exploitation ecosystem is sufficient and robust

The primary project-project relationship to be established is with RM-ROADMAP's 'sister' project funded on the same call [HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20], "CARDEA". Both consortia share a willingness to collaborate for the good of the RM community where synergies exist and have engaged early in the projects to develop a formal understanding. This will include the following principles

related to DCE:

- I. CARDEA and RM ROADMAP will link to each other's tools and websites where relevant as soon as it is reasonably implementable. Both projects will initially include links and information on each other's projects on individual websites.
- II. With respect to project results and based on preliminary discussions between RM Roadmap and CARDEA project coordinators, there will be only one online tool repository for training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities for research managers so that there is a clear understanding of where to find reliable and complete information.
- III. Each project will be represented on the other's advisory board, under the appropriate non-disclosure terms, to ensure opportunities for further integration are captured.

Other projects that have the potential to cluster on similar terms with RM-ROADMAP (and by extension, CARDEA), are listed in Appendix A. Contact will be initiated through our community-building activities. If a sufficient number of projects engage, a clustering board will be considered as described in the project plan, facilitated through the KCP.

These include many projects funded under the broader call of HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01: "Reforming and Enhancing the European R&I System, part of the Horizon Europe's "Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area" call (Destination 3). The partners will scan future iterations of calls under this Destination for new initiatives.

4. COMMUNICATIONS PLAN AND CONTENT

4.1. Roles and Protocols

As WP4 leaders, CHX have general responsibility for managing communications activities.

- Communication is talking to the outside world about the project, using information already in the public domain.
- Compliance is governed by Article 17 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement; partners must:
 - acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate); the EU flag must be at least as prominent as other logos.
 - include the disclaimer:
 - "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them."
 - If communication is expected to have "major media impact", the coordinator must be notified so they can inform the Project Officer in advance.

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- Presentation slides, poster designs for printing and videos will be provided to be used by the partners without needing further permission.
- In order to coordinate, promote and support compliance in communication activities, partners should notify the C&D lead as soon as a communication activity is planned, by emailing rmroadmap@crowdhelix.com and/or updating the online tracker found on EMDesk
- To multiply the benefit of individual activities, take photos and videos which can be used for other content (e.g. newsletter, social media)
- Following the activity, partners are required to update or complete the project tracker;
 - Add/confirm details including date, location, audience type and size.
 - Report social media campaigns (a significant post or series of posts clearly linked to the project on your own channel) as a single activity; ensure that you have access to the reach statistics.
- Partners are required to record specific costs related to these activities, as they will be requested with the financial report.

4.2. Identity and support materials

The project identity has been developed, including a logo and document templates.

Figure 2: RM-ROADMAP logos and headers

A set of slides using this identity containing project information is provided that can be used without further additional permission and will be maintained and updated as RM-ROADMAP progresses.

4.3. Website

During the initiation phase for DCE, the RM-ROADMAP website is only required to display information about the project and the partners, and to encourage visitors to engage with the project by following social media accounts and/or providing contact details for newsletters and direct communication. To include active content, up-to-date news from the project's social media will be mirrored on the page.

A single page website (<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>) went live on October 28th, 2022 (Figure 2). With respect to the formal project plan, this represents achieving Milestone 1. An additional page on the Ambassadors programme was added in December 2022.

During later DCE phases of implementation and sustaining, the website will transform into a gateway to the Knowledge and Community Platform.

Figure 3: RM-ROADMAP Webpage (screen capture January 2023)

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Figure 4: RM-ROADMAP Webpage statistics (October 28 2022 - January 9 2023)

4.4. Social Media

The project plan proposed three social media channels would be established: Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. Considering experience from the partners currently performing other Horizon actions, the consortium agreed that Facebook was no longer an appropriate or worthwhile platform for RM-ROADMAP. As an alternative, a project home on ResearchGate will be set up.

The @rmroadmap handle is secured on all three platforms. During the initiation phase,

- twitter.com/RMROADMAP (Operated by CHX)
- www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap/ (Operated by CHX)
- www.researchgate.net/project/RM-ROADMAP (operated by HETFA)

During DCE initiation, these channels will be used to engage with relevant accounts, and resharing information with the primary intent of building a following. In later phases, the channels will be used for dissemination and as a facilitator for stakeholder/community engagement.

4.5. Newsletter

Project newsletters will be released once per year using MailChimp, to an assembled direct email list (with appropriate permissions obtained) and via social media. The first will be scheduled to align with the first release of information about the ambassador programme (WP3) and KCP (WP4).

4.6. Press and traditional media

An initial press release at project kick-off was featured in Research Professional and posted to the coordinator and several partner websites.

Further media engagement will follow project activity. The main targets are the relevant research business publications of Research Professional and Science Business. Popularised science publishing platforms (Horizon Magazine, The Conversation) may also be appropriate.

Research management roadmap project 'ready to launch'

Earma-led initiative has EU backing of €1.5 million

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A project to set out the future direction of European research management is ready to launch, the organisations leading it have announced.

The RM-Roadmap [has won €1.5 million from the EU](#) for work that "aims to define" the future of the research management profession.

Led by the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators, the project will draft a vision and strategy for research management, establish a stakeholder community and aim to build synergies between resources.

"The community remains fragmented, and recognition varies across Europe," said Earma managing director Nik Claesen. "I believe now is the right time to connect our existing European networks and create the roadmap for the future of research management in Europe."

"Later in the year we begin recruiting volunteers to co-create this roadmap by forming an ambassador network, and also build an intelligent platform to support our community on this exciting journey."

Mission support

Michael Browne, representing Crowdhelix, a research networking organisation participating in the project, said the initiative would include work on how research managers can support the EU research and innovation-based 'missions' on cancer, climate change, oceans, soil and cities.

"Research managers are a vital part of delivering research impact, strategic planning and bridging between leadership groups in complex university and research organisations," he said.

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<https://www.researchprofessional.com/0/news/europe/universities/2022/7/Research-management-roadmap-project-ready-to-launch.html>

Figure 5: RM-ROADMAP Pre-KO Press Release featured in Research Professional (14 July 2022)

4.7. Events

During RM-ROADMAP three main events / event series are envisaged, as described in Table 2 below.

Partners will also participate in international research management conferences, seminars, and workshops (Appendix B) and will also endeavour to represent RM-ROADMAP at regional meetings and events, to convey the regional dimension of the project and potential links to Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3).

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Event type	Description	Timing
RM-Roadmap Workshop	Ambassadors, invited key stakeholders and cluster project representatives will meet once per year for an update on RM-ROADMAP progress, strategic discussions and to receive training on moderating the KCP and advocating for RM-ROADMAP at national/regional level	Annual
RM Helix event	Helix events are designed to generate discussion in the community of followers established on the Crowdhelix platform. A typical agenda features short briefs on exploitable results, pitches for new projects targeting open funding calls, and breakout discussions on emerging topics. The nature and objectives of each annual Helix event will be determined after the RM Helix is launched. Helix events may be virtual, or in person if co-located with another relevant Crowdhelix member event.	Annual
RM-Roadmap final event	Virtual conference to disseminate the results of RM-ROADMAP to stakeholders, including the project co-creation community, policy makers and partners engaging for further collaboration.	M34-M36

5. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

5.1. Roles and Protocols

As WP4 leader, CHX has general responsibility for reporting on dissemination activities. Disseminating of own results in compliance with the following protocols is the responsibility of each partner.

- Dissemination is sharing the results of the project outside of the consortium in a publicly available format.
- Results are: *"Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights"*.
- From the Grant Agreement, Article 17 states the obligation to disseminate, further detailed on Annex 5 describing Open Science protocols.
- Dissemination is subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests; therefore additional provisions are contained in the Consortium Agreement - these are to allow publication, not prevent it.
- Dissemination can be by any means: journal articles, conference presentations, white papers etc.
 - Partners are advised to limit disclosure of project results to formal publishing platforms. Social media, blog posts, interviews are difficult to monitor and control, and should therefore be used only for Communication as in the previous section. If you wish to disseminate in this way, contact the C&D lead.

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- For journal articles and conference submissions where the full article is submitted for peer review, send the final version of the article to rmroadmap@crowdhelix.com at least 30 days in advance of publication.
- A formal notice is sent to all partners containing the submission, with a deadline for objections no less than 30 days later.
- Objections must be specific and have corrective actions; i.e. either:
 - Remove confidential information.
 - Identify details that could prevent successful exploitation project results, needing a delay of up to 90 days to put protection in place.
- With no valid objections, the publication can proceed.
- For conferences where only an abstract is submitted:
 - If the abstract discloses project results, you must share it for review as per the above process prior to submission.
 - If the abstract only describes in general what will be presented, ensure a description of the content of your presentation is shared for review according to the above timelines prior to the actual presentation or event.
- In all cases, discuss planned dissemination with the project partners at appropriate meetings well in advance.
- On Open Access for publications:
 - All peer-reviewed scientific publications relating must, at the latest at the time of publication, have the final peer-reviewed manuscript deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
 - Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to their articles to be able to comply.
 - Only publication fees (“APCs”) in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for claim under the project.
 - The [Directory of Open Journals](#) lists compliant venues for publishing.
- On Open Data:
 - Governed by the Data Management Plan (D5.2).
- Other:
 - Follow the Vancouver Rules for authorship.
 - Abide by the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment principles, in particular with respect to journal metrics.

5.2. Scientific Publications and Conferences

Target journals for RM-ROADMAP publications are listed in Appendix C. Events featuring peer-reviewed scientific content are included in the target schedule, Appendix B.

To track the longer-term impact of scientific publications, and to facilitate sustained publishing of RM-Roadmap results beyond the project’s funded term, a home will be established on a suitable Open

Access Repository service, for example Zenodo or Figshare.

6. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

6.1. Roles and Protocols

As WP6 leaders, ASTP have general responsibility for exploitation planning and management.

- **Exploitation** is use of the results outside of the project, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, standardisation or policy-making activities, and further research and innovation actions.
- As defined earlier for dissemination, **results** are: "*Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights*".
- Provisions for Joint Ownership of results are found in the Consortium Agreement
- Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement states that:
 - funded beneficiaries must — up to four years after the end of the action — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.
- If the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the results must be published to the Horizon Results Platform (HRP).
- Adding Results to the HRP is the responsibility of the coordinator, and may require following the Dissemination protocols in the previous section.
- The HRP accepts only Key Exploitable Results (KERs), defined as Results selected due to high potential to be exploited, based on degree of innovation, availability, and potential impact.

6.2. Key Exploitable Results

Two Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are envisaged from RM-ROADMAP. During DCE initiation, KERs are described, located within the project workplan, and an initial assessment of their impact pathway performed (Table 2).

In later phases, through the tasks of WP6, detailed plans for sustained exploitation of the KERs will be explored, and strategic action plans put in place to maximise the likelihood of exploitation and potential value realised from the results.

Further KERs may be identified and assessed in the course of the project execution.

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KER description	Produced by	Impact Pathway(s)
Roadmap: A summary of all findings of the RM-ROADMAP activities, to provide input for EU and national policy making, with specific attention to the European Research Area and Widening participation. The primary European roadmap will also include national, regional and/or thematic annexes.	Task 3.4 (EARMA)	Key stakeholders including policy makers, EU and national funding agencies, strategic university groups, national governments, RM associations to receive, digest and enact recommendations from the roadmap in their next cycle.
KCP: A platform for the RM community, with functions and features including (not limited to) member directory, moderated discussion forums, opportunity matching, events calendars, training course & provider marketplace, knowledge repositories. With associated training material.	Task 4.6 (EARMA lead with CHX support)	RM users, training providers and other stakeholders to be defined continue to desire access to the KCP beyond the project term. A set of possible business plans will be developed within WP6 to identify and evaluate long-term commercial models and potential owners, within the consortium and outside. Access could be provided on eg. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - freemium model (basic or limited features to users at no cost , with premium for supplemental or advanced features) - Subscription membership/licensing model whereby RMs, RPOs or RFOs would pay to access; - funded and licensed at an EU level; - Commercially subsidized by training providers advertising on the platform

Table 2: KER Initiation

6.3. Barriers to exploitation and response strategies

In later phases of the project, exploitation tools such as SWOT analyses and impact/business canvases may be used in the further assessment of KER strategies, beyond the initial view in presented in Table 3.

Barrier, possible outcome and severity	RM-Roadmap Response
Lack of engagement by governments and national policy makers	Stakeholder mapping initiated in the early stages of the project to identify key organisations in policy making, and determine interest / influence on the project. UNA Europa as an associate partner represent an existing link to the EC on all topics linked to the broader collaboration and education as well as links with the national policy makers.
Absence of active/identifiable communities or parts of the RM communities in certain countries:	RM ROADMAP Ambassadors will seek to to facilitate the creation of networks and communities within their home

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	countries. Where a community struggles to build, neighbouring / similar profile countries with strong RM organisations may be used to bridge the gap.
Lack of interest of RFOs, RPOs and/or RTOs in the KCP	Early and repeated invitation to participate in project activities. RM ROADMAP Ambassadors specifically tasked with building interest.
Unable to publish training materials on the platform	Rights negotiation with training providers to encourage open sharing where possible, followed by transparent categorisation of material by access rights and cost.
Lack of engagement in the project activities of RM from the WIDENING Countries:	Leverage existing successful networks including BESTPRAC, which organises bi-annual meetings with great involvement from RM in the widening countries.

Table 3: Barriers to exploitation and responses

7. MILESTONES AND PERFORMANCE MONITORING

ACTIVITIES	Objective	Milestone / Schedule	Key Performance Indicator(s)	Target (end of project unless otherwise stated)
Research Management Helix	Establish an active community of cross-discipline and cross-sector stakeholders, suitable for project dissemination and impact acceleration activities	Scoping from M1; established in line with KCP; maintained at least 5 years beyond the project or as long as valuable	Number of organisations represented in followers	150
Project website	Display project key facts to a general audience. Direct specific audiences to other channels (eg KCP, social media, mailing list, direct contact)	M1 onwards and 5 years beyond the term [Project Milestone 1]	Number of visits	2000
Social media	Three channels actively posting relevant content	Establish at project KO	Number of followers	300 followers across Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate
			Impressions (general public reach)	20 000
Partners' websites	Each partner to be conveying project information to their own audience	As defined by partners task involvement	Number of pages	1 dedicated webpage area per partner website
Newsletters	Share projects activities, disseminate results, and encourage engagement from interested audiences via mailing list (self-signup) and social media	One per year starting M12	Open rate per newsletter to mailing list	25% open rate per newsletter
			Number of views on social media.	(No target)

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ACTIVITIES	Objective	Milestone / Schedule	Key Performance Indicator(s)	Target (end of project unless otherwise stated)
Media Engagement	Share project activities, multiply communications, and calls to action, acknowledge funding sources	Continuous before, during and after project	Number of press releases / popular articles	6
			Number of media appearances per partner	6
Project workshops	Share project activities & engage with stakeholders	Annual	Number of overall participants	>80 per workshop
			Events attended by policy representatives	4
Project final conference	Virtual event to share project results &, engage with stakeholders	M34	Number of participants	>200
Other international events	Showcase RM-ROADMAP, share progress, and disseminate results to target audiences (i.e academic conferences, professional association fairs and events)	As per target event schedule (Appendix B)	Number of participations / appearances	10 (NB this amalgamates general int'l and professional event targets in GA Part II)
Other regional events	Showcase RM-ROADMAP, share progress and disseminate results with a focus on the regional dimension of the project		Number of participations / appearances per partner	6
Publications	Disseminate project results to relevant target groups through scientific, professional and/or popular publications	As results are available; continues beyond project term	Number of articles	10

Table 4: Performance measures, linked objectives and targets for DCE.

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Appendix A: Relevant Projects for Clustering

Relationship owners will be assigned as initial contact is made.

Project Name	Funding call	Status	Topic	RM-Roadmap Owner	Link
CARDEA	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20	Active	RM Training & Networking	EARMA	
RoadSTEAMer	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70	Active	STEAM		
SENSE	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70	Active	STEAM		
The Seer	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70	Active	STEAM		
stoRM	Erasmus+	Closed	RM Training & Networking	CHX	
Management of Collaborative R+D+I Projects	National (Portugal)	Active	Project management	NOVA	https://agenciadeinovacao.limesurvey.net/988343
ECS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-60	Active	Citizen Science		
IMPETUS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-61	Active	Citizen Science		
INSPIRE	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-80	Active	Equality, diversity, welfare, values		
GENDERACTIONplus	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-81	Active	Equality, diversity, welfare, values		
foRMation	Erasmus+	Active	RM Training & Networking	HETFa	
IANUS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44	Active	Ethics & Integrity		
POIESIS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44	Active	Ethics & Integrity		
Veritas	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44	Active	Ethics & Integrity		
PREPARED	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-90	Active	Ethics & Integrity		
Path2Integrity	SwafS-02-2018	Closed	Ethics & Integrity		
iRECS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-91	Active	Ethics & Integrity		

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PathOS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-91	Active	Open Research		
OPUS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-45	Active	Open Research		
DIAMAS	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-43	Active	Open Research		
WorldFAIR	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41	Active	Open Research		
hsbooster.eu	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-32	Active	Standards		
SOPS4RI	SwafS-03-2018	Closed	Ethics & Integrity		https://sops4ri.eu/
USTREAM	Erasmus+	Closed	HEI Organisation		https://eua.eu/resources/projects/607-ustream.html
NEWLEAD	Erasmus+	Active	HEI Organisation		https://unileaders.eu/en/about/
ERASMUS+ ADMIN	Erasmus+	Closed	RM Training & Networking		
V4+WB Network	International Visegrad Fund	Closed	RM Training & Networking	HETFA	https://hetfa.eu/international-projects/v4wb-rmas/

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Appendix B: Target Event Schedule

Date	Description	Location	Open to
30-Mar-22	V4+WB RMA Network Final Conference	Budapest, Hungary	
24-Nov-22	ASTP EU Workshop	Virtual	
30-Nov-22	foRMAtion final conference	Brussels, Belgium	
12-Jan-23	CrowdHelix RTO event 2023	London, UK	CrowdHelix members and guests
24-Apr-23	EARMA 2023	Prague, Czechia	EARMA members and guests
30-May-23	INORMS 2023	Durban, South Africa	Open
01-Apr-24	EARMA 2024	Madrid, Spain	EARMA members and guests
01-May-24	INORMS 2024	Madrid, Spain	Open
01-Sep-24	EU Research and innovation days	Virtual	

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Appendix C: Target publications and OA policies

CHX take no responsibility for this information; partners should verify details on OA compliance and APC eligibility themselves before publishing.

Venue	ISSN	OA Compliance	APC (indicative)
Journal of Research Management and Administration	2753-9245	Yes - full	Nil
NCURA Research Management Review	?	?	Nil
Journal of Research Management and Governance	2637-1103	Yes - but check copyright on submission	Nil
Journal of Research Administration – SRAI	2573-7104	No - copyright issue	Nil
Journal of European Public Policy	1466-4429	Yes – hybrid	€ 3 190*
Perspectives on European Politics and Society	2374-5126	Yes – hybrid	€ 2 370*
Journal of European Integration	1477-2280	Yes – hybrid	€ 2 370*
Open Research Europe	2732-5121	Yes	Nil

(*) Ineligible as a direct cost as journal is not fully open

RM ROADMAP

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